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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Funded by

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Publication date	Author	Change
1.0	13.12.2022	Camilla Silveira	Initial version

List of Acronyms

ANTT - Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo

CIDOC CRM - CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model

DGFP - General Administration of National Treasury

DGLAB - General Directorate for Book, Archives and Libraries

DigitArq - Portuguese Archive Database

DMP – Data Management Plan

DOI - Digital Object Identifier

EPISA – Entity and Property Inference for Semantic Archives

FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology

ICA - International Council on Archives

INESC TEC - Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science

ISAD - International Standard Archival Description

OCR - Optical character recognition

OWL - Web Ontology Language

RDF - Resource Description Framework

RiC - Return on Integrated Communication

SIO - Semantic Interpretation Ontology

SNI - National Secretariat of Information

SPARQL - Standard Query Language and Protocol for Linked Open Data

SWLR - Semantic Web Language Rules

XML- Extensible Markup Language

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1. Introduction

The EPISA project – Entity and Property Inference for Semantic Archives – treads an essential path in the national panorama towards the accessibility of the Portuguese cultural heritage and information in general.

The purpose of the project is to create a new description model for archives and to promote the semiautomatic creation of metadata. Its main goal is to incorporate the national archives in the global network of semantic linked data.

The project is being developed by INESC TEC (Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science), in partnership with the University of Évora and DGLAB (General Directorate for Book, Archives and Libraries), under the coordination of Professors Carla Teixeira Lopes and Cristina Ribeiro.

With a duration of four years, the EPISA project is being funded by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) since 2019.

Objectives:

- Create a new description model for archives, based on models already proposed for museums and archives;
- Support archival description in the semi-automatic creation of metadata;
- Migrate existing ISAD-standard archival descriptions to standards compliant with the CIDOC-CRM (museums) and RiC (ICA) model;
- Incorporate the archives in the global network of semantic linked data;
- Link archival data to other information sources;
- Propose interfaces that enable a more efficient interaction, for specialists, for general users and for machines;
- Promote the presence of national archives in international aggregators;
- Facilitate access to archives/cultural heritage;
- Facilitate access to information.

Tasks:

1. Project management and dissemination of results;
2. Linked data model for cultural content;
3. Semantic migration with relations inference;
4. Knowledge propagation;
5. Document mining for automatic metadata records;
6. Knowledge graph management platform;
7. Exploration and querying interface;
8. User evaluation.

2. Data Summary

2.1. What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Below is a brief summary of the project's datasets. In order to facilitate the display of the information, the datasets have been numbered. This numeration does not follow a chronological order of creation.

Will you re-use any existing data and how? What is the origin of the data?

Answers to the above questions are integrated in section 2.1., when applicable.

Dataset 01: “Typewritten Digital Representations of Portuguese Cultural Heritage Documents from the 20th century” (<https://doi.org/10.25747/ZC25-1531>). Author: Mariana Dias. It has typewritten Portuguese documents extracted from the Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo (<https://digitarq.arquivos.pt/>), which includes records from two fonds of the 20th century: the General Administration of National Treasury (DGFP) and the National Secretariat of Information (SNI). The digital representation of documents in the archives can have multiple one-page digital representations. In total, were extracted 8.115 archival records with 27.017 one-page digital representations. The digital representations were classified by writing format (handwritten, typewritten, or blank), as some archival records contain handwritten or blank documents that are not relevant to our work. The dataset has 23.794 typewritten digital representations, 1.681 handwritten digital representations, and 1.542 blank digital representations. Furthermore, the dataset was classified into ten types of digital representations: letters, structured reports, non-structured reports, processes' covers, minutes' covers, minutes' content, books' covers, books' content, theatre plays' covers, and theatre plays' content. Identifying digital representation typologies relevant to the OCR task was carried out by observing existing textual descriptions of the records and document layouts of the digital representations. The classification of the dataset was performed manually. The typewritten dataset has 3.264 letters, 6.560 structured reports, 1.970 non-structured reports, 82 covers of processes, 6 covers of minutes, 1.473 contents

of minutes, 19 books' covers, 182 books' contents, 165 theatre play' covers, and 8.845 theatre play' contents.

Dataset 02: “Manual Transcriptions of Typewritten Digital Representations of Portuguese Cultural Heritage Documents from the 20th Century” (<https://doi.org/10.25747/wpna-je39>). Author: Margarida Falcão. It includes manual transcriptions of typewritten digital representations of Portuguese cultural heritage documents from the 20th century, extracted from the Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo (ANTT) (<https://digitarq.arquivos.pt/>). It has records from two funds: the General Administration of National Treasury (DGFP) and the National Secretariat of Information (SNI). The manual transcriptions of the digital representations will be used for the text recognition evaluation process to create tools that can facilitate the work of cultural heritage professionals by extracting and describing specific objects in an automated way. The digital representations were extracted from a dataset previously developed (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2022-004>). Were selected 708 out of 12.041 typewritten digital representations from 5 document types: letters, structured reports, non-structured reports, processes covers, and theatre plays covers. The dataset has 162 letters, 328 structured reports, 98 non-structured reports, 60 processes covers, and 60 theatre plays covers.

Dataset 03: “CIDOC-CRM Ontology Representation of the Portuguese Archival Description Unit Obtained From the Semantic Migration Process of DigitArq” (<https://doi.org/10.25747/bsw1-tq51>). Authors: Dora Melo, Irene Pimenta Rodrigues and Davide Varagnolo. This dataset includes an excerpt of the CIDOC-CRM Ontology Representation of the DigitArq records from Bragança District Archive, two SPARQL query examples - "What are the locals and their parishes located in the county 'Bragança' between 1900 and 1910?" and "What is the number of children per couple, between 1800 and 1850?", to facilitate the ontology exploration. Also, a Semantic Migration of Fonds Examples, namely "Paróquia de Aldoar" (<http://pesquisa.adporto.arquivos.pt/details?id=488455>), with reference code "PT/ADPRT/PRQ/PPRT01" and "Juízo da Índia e Mina" (<http://digitarq.arquivos.pt/details?id=4208377>), with reference code "PT/TT/JIM". As well as, Installation Unit - REGISTOS DE BAPTISMOS, which is a CIDOC-CRM

Ontology Representation of the Portuguese Archival Description Unit, entitled "Registos de Baptimos" (<http://pesquisa.adporto.arquivos.pt/details?id=488469>), with reference code "PT/ADPRT/PRQ/PPRT01/001/0004". This dataset is part of the results obtained from the semantic migration process of DigitArq - Portuguese Archive Database - metadata into CIDOC-CRM Ontology representation.

Dataset 04: “Discourse Ontology for Incorporation/Transference Events” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/en/dataset/cs-2022-011>). Authors: Dora Melo and Irene Pimenta Rodrigues. It is an OWL ontology, a semantic interpretation ontology (SIO), that contains the concepts and relations used in natural language sentences describing these events. The ontology also contains a set of semantic web language rules (SWLR) to model dates. This dataset is part of the results obtained from the semantic migration process of DigitArq - Portuguese Archive Database - metadata into CIDOC-CRM Ontology representation.

Dataset 05: “ISAD(G) Descriptions of Archival Records with Entity Annotation” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2022-013>). Author: Vasco Gomes. This dataset contains long text ISAD(G) fields from records from the Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo annotated with entities. It was built to evaluate the effectiveness of data migration from ISAD(G) to ArchOnto in the EPISA project. Thus, a set of long text fields present in DigitArq was annotated, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of data migration from the old system to the new one. In order to obtain structured metadata that constitute an added value for the semantic migration, elements of ISAD(G) were considered. To this end, a study was carried out on the description of existing records in DigitArq, which complies with ISAD(G) and ISAAR(CPF) archival description standards.

Dataset 06: “Analysis of the DigitArq archive record entities and their properties in Wikidata and in DBpedia” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2023-003>). Author: Camilla Silveira. This dataset, which is the product of a master's dissertation (<https://hdl.handle.net/10216/143034>), analyzed a sample of 25 records from the Portuguese National Archives (<https://digitarq.arquivos.pt/>), chosen by archival specialists as representative of different fonds and description levels, to identify entities and properties and explore relationships with other non-archival resources. After selecting the entities in the records, Wikidata and DBpedia databases were chosen for data enrichment and linking. The analysis of the entities in the records provided hundreds

of properties directly related to classes in the corresponding databases. A more significant set of properties was obtained by selecting properties that had more data entered into the databases for entities of the corresponding classes. These entities and properties were then subjected to tests using Wikidata Query Service and DBpedia SPARQL Explorer. The goal of this data generation was to provide additional information to improve the search interfaces of archival information systems helping to optimize information retrieval to the benefit of archivists and users.

Dataset 07: “User evaluation of the DigitArq and DigitArq+ interfaces” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2023-002>). Author: Margarida Gouveia Augusto. This dataset is part of a dissertation entitled "Evaluation of the migration of archival records to linked data in the EPISA project" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10216/143042>). The datasets were generated in an experiment with two groups of users (common users and archivists) of both DigitArq platform interface and DigitArq+, a new interface developed in the EPISA project. A script with different questions was developed to evaluate the quality of access and search behavior. DigitArq is the research platform of the National Archives of Torre do Tombo, that enables users to remotely access certain services, such as viewing scanned documents or reserving documents to be consulted in person.

Dataset 08: “Analysis of baptism, marriage and death registers belonging to the District Archives of Guarda, the District Archives of Porto and deferred passports from the District Archives of Bragança” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2022-014>). Author: Margarida Gouveia Augusto. The content of the datasets has description units related to baptisms, marriages and deaths from the District Archive of Guarda; baptisms, marriages and deaths from the District Archive of Porto; and, finally, deferred passports from the District Archive of Bragança. The analyzed records belonging to the District Archive of Guarda are present in a fonds called "Paróquia da Sé - Guarda 1860/1911-03-31" which contains seven series. However, only the series related to baptisms, marriages and deaths were analyzed. The records belonging to the District Archive of Porto are present in a fonds called "Paróquia de Aldoar 1640-05-15/1911-03-31" which contains six series. However, only the series concerning baptisms, marriages and deaths were analyzed. The analyzed records from the Bragança District Archive are present in a fonds named "Governo Civil de Bragança 1834/1986", which contains 843 books and 123 bundles.

This collection is composed by twenty sections, namely one section called “Passaportes 1844/1969” where the series with the analyzed records of deferred passports can be found. This series - entitled “Registo de passaportes deferidos 1844-09-10/1969-03-24” - has 43 installation units. In turn, these installation units have between 76 and 3392 documents.

Dataset 09: “Consensual ArchOnto representation of 13 Portuguese Historical Archival Records based on their Digital Representations” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2023-001>). Author: Mariana Dias. The dataset contains archival descriptions represented in the ArchOnto model (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2022-004>) of 13 records from the 20th century with typewritten digital representations. We selected a sample of 13 records from a previously developed dataset (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2022-004>) that extracted typewritten digital representations from the Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo (<https://digitarq.arquivos.pt/>). Afterwards, two archivists from Direção-Geral do Livro, dos Arquivos e das Bibliotecas (DGLAB) performed the descriptions, and upon discussion, we reached a consensual description. The main criterion for the description is that it must be solely focused on textual content visible in the digital representations.

Dataset 10: “ArchOnto ontology representation of Portuguese archival description units (baptism records and passports)” (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt/dataset/cs-2023-006>). Authors: Catarina Pires, Inês Koch, Sérgio Nunes. The content of the datasets includes an excerpt of the ArchOnto ontology representation of the DigitArq baptisms records from Bragança District Archive and passports. These datasets, represented in ArchOnto, were obtained through an automatic transformation from the CIDOC-CRM ontology representation. The initial records, represented in CIDOC-CRM, were the result of a migration process of records obtained from the DigitArq - Portuguese Archive Database. The migration from CIDOC-CRM to ArchOnto was made using SPARQL update queries. The datasets include the ArchOnto ontology representation of the DigitArq baptisms records from Bragança District Archive from 1644 to 1911, and passports records from 1914 to 1918. Also, contains the ArchOnto Ontology version used and its sub-ontologies (CIDOC-CRM, N-ary, DataObject, Link2DataObject, and ISAD Ontology).

2.2. What types, formats, and expected sizes of data will the project generate/collect?

Dataset	Type	Format	Size
Typewritten Digital Representations of Portuguese Cultural Heritage Documents from the 20th century	Images and associated files	.zip with *.tif, .csv	.zip 5,64 GB; .csv 109 KB
Manual Transcriptions of Typewritten Digital Representations of Portuguese Cultural Heritage Documents from the 20th Century	Text, textual descriptors, documents	.zip with *.tif .zip with *.txt, .csv, .txt	.zip 130 MB;.zip 450 KB; .csv 6.85 GB; .txt 3KB
CIDOC-CRM Ontology Representation of the Portuguese Archival Description Unit Obtained From the Semantic Migration Process of DigitArq	text	.xml; .rdf; .owl; txt; .sparql	.xml 1KB; .rdf 455 KB; .owl 18 KB; .owl 2 MB; .sparql 1KB; .xml 2 KB; .owl 182 KB; .owl 18 MB; .owl 1 MB;
Discourse Ontology for Incorporation/Transference Events	text	.owl	115 KB
ISAD(G) Descriptions of Archival Records With Entity Annotation	text	.json; txt	.json 92KB; .json 19KB; .json 263KB; .json 371KB; .json 495KB; .json 234KB; .json 2KB; .json 5KB; .json 7KB; .json 12KB; .json 5KB; .txt 5KB

Dataset	Type	Format	Size
Analysis of the DigitArq archive record entities and their properties in Wikidata and in DBpedia	text	.xlsx, .pdf	.xlsx 21KB; .xlsx 22KB; .pdf 67 KB
User evaluation of the DigitArq and DigitArq+ interfaces	text	.xlsx, .pdf	.xlsx 40KB; .pdf 2,280 KB
Analysis of baptism, marriage and death registers belonging to the District Archives of Guarda, the District Archives of Porto and deferred passports from the District Archives of Bragança	text	.xlsx, .docx	.xlsx 956KB; .xlsx 3,590KB; .xlsx 29KB; .xlsx 356KB; .xlsx 17KB; .docx 18KB
Consensual ArchOnto representation of 13 Portuguese Historical Archival Records based on their Digital Representations	text	.zip with *.tiff, .zip with *.owl, .md	.zip 759,100KB; .zip 42 KB; .md 4KB
ArchOnto ontology representation of Portuguese archival description units (baptism records and passports)	text	.zip with *.owl; .zip with *.owl; .zip with *.rdf	.zip 719KB; .zip 84KB; .zip 90KB

Table 1: Types, formats, and expected sizes of data.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Each dataset produced during the project will have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to enable its further identification and location. Also, search keywords will be provided to optimize the possibilities of re-using the data.

In order to standardize file naming, it will be suggested that project team members adopt the following practices when naming their files:

- Files should be named systematically;
- Avoid special characters or spaces in a file name, and instead of periods or spaces or slashes use capitals and underscores;
- Use date format: YYYYMMDD;
- Include a version number.

Elements to consider using in a naming convention are: date of creation, project name, type or work, location, sample, analysis, name of the creator, version number. Examples:

20160104_EPISAProject_Test1_SilveiraC_v1.xlsx

2016-01-04_EPISAProject_ExperimentName_InstrumentName_ImageID.tif

20160104_EPISAProject_MeetingNotes_SilveiraC_v2.docx

The metadata for general research data will follow the Dublin Core Metadata, and the following metadata will be provided: dc.Title, dc.Creator, dc.DateModified, dc.DateSubmitted, dc.BibliographicCitation, dc.Identifier, dc.Coverage.Spatial, dc.Coverage.Temporal, dc.Created, dc.FileSize, dc.Format, dc.Language, dc.Type, dc.Source, dc.Relation, dc.Contributor, dc.License, dc.Subject, dc.Publisher.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

The data collected and created during the project is exclusive and very specific, therefore, very important to be preserved for use by other researchers, research performing organizations and for educational purposes. The project data will be preserved to ensure complete documentation and reproducible data, securing the reuse of the data in different applications.

For this reason, the files associated with the datasets will be licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. This means that data may be shared, copied and modified if appropriate credit is given, a link to the CC BY license is provided, and it indicates whether changes have been made. If the material is remixed, transformed, or something is built upon the material, it must be distributed under the same license as the original. Likewise, legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything that the license permits cannot be applied.

All the data will be preserved at the INESC TEC institutional repository (<https://rdm.inesctec.pt>) for at least 5 years after the end of the project completion (at least until 2027). After the five-year period, the viability of long-term preservation of the same data in another repository will be analysed. And if necessary, this information will be added in a new version of the DMP.

The data contained in the datasets can be accessed with Microsoft Excel or similar open office tools, text editors, image viewers, pdf viewers, and the open-source ontology editor and knowledge management system: Protégé. It supports a variety of formats, including OWL, RDF and XML Schema.

4. Data security

For data protection purposes, it will be suggested that three copies of all project data be stored in at least two geographically distributed locations. One of these locations will be the INESC TEC institutional repository. The second storage location could be the project team's personal computers, an external hard drive or a file hosting service that offers cloud storage. The adoption of a regular backup schedule will also be suggested, as well as testing to assure that the stored data files can be recovered.

5. How the data will be disseminated

The project will generate data that may be of interest and use by researchers, students, research institutions and others. Thus, the data collected and created during the project will be disseminated on the project website (<https://episa.inesctec.pt/>); in INESC TEC institutional repository; through papers and publications in scientific journals, conferences and seminars; through bachelor and master dissertations, PhD theses and media mentions (blogs).

In order to make the data more usable and more easily interpretable by others, it will be disseminated using standard approaches, accompanied by metadata and associated code. To support this process, many journals and repositories provide guidelines for how data can be properly cited, with digital object identifiers and recommended formats.

6. Responsibilities

6.1. Responsible entities

Principal (coordinating) institution:

INESC TEC - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência (INESCTEC) (Contact person: Carla Teixeira Lopes).

Participating Institutions:

- The General Directorate of Books, Archives and Libraries (DGLAB) (Contact person: Silvestre Lacerda);
- The University of Évora (Contact person: Irene Rodrigues).

6.2. Responsible persons

Responsible for the collection of the data: Camilla Silveira.

Responsible for the processing of the data: Camilla Silveira.

Responsible for backups: The system administrators of the INESC TEC are responsible for the backups related to the INESC TEC research data repository.

Responsible for publishing and sharing data: João Castro (INESC TEC).

Responsible for DMP creation: Camilla Silveira (ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4073-7616>).

7. Ethics and legal compliance

The EPISA project complies with all requirements related to Research Data Management and Personal Data Protection. No ethical or legal issues are foreseen for any of the datasets generated and which will be shared according to the international Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable is the first version of the EPISA Data Management Plan and contains a description of the datasets collected and generated during the project. The described datasets were explored by different tasks throughout the project. In case an update of the information about the dataset, sharing, preservation and dissemination aspects is needed, the information will be included in future versions of the current document.